

Management

STRATEGY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST VILLAGE IN BALI ISLAND

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Abstract

The Indonesian government is promoting the development of the potential of villages through the tourism village program, but the formation of a tourism village requires prior study to assess its feasibility as a tourism destination. This study aims to analyze the potential and develop strategies for developing Babahan Village in Tabanan Regency, Bali Province as a culture-based tourism village. This research is a qualitative descriptive study which begins with data collection of tourism potential using SWOT analysis and continued with the IFAS-EFAS method. IFAS-EFAS calculation results show the strength factors of the development of Babahan Village as a culture-based ecotourism village are : having a tracking path (0.305), good natural potential (0.305), the existence of Besikalung Temple (0.302), and beautiful rice field views (0.300). SWOT matrix analysis is in Quadrant I (Supporting Aggressive Strategies) with the results of four Strengths-Opportunities (SO) development strategies, namely: a). maintaining and improving the quality of tourist attraction, b). develop and organize the natural potential that exists, c). improve the quality of service to tourists, d). development of tour packages. The conclusion is Babahan Village, Tabanan Regency, Bali has the potential to be developed into a tourism village.

Keywords: Tourism Village; Culture-Based; SWOT Analysis; IFAS-EFAS.

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1. Introduction

Tourism policies that have only focused on the number of tourist visits have threatened the sustainability Balinese environment and culture. This fact has raised awareness of the importance of tourism development that is oriented towards environmental sustainability and based on the ability of local communities. This shift in orientation is motivated by the awareness that the development of tourism at the present time must pay attention to environmental issues, empowering local communities and long-term oriented sustainable development. Related to these issues, the concept of cultural-based ecotourism can be the solution.

According to Damanik and Weber (2006), ecotourism is a tourism activity that is responsible for the welfare of the local community and environmental preservation. Ecotourism emerges as a solution to the concerns of conventional tourism which tends to pursue economic benefits and ignores the social aspects and environmental sustainability (Fennell, 2008). According to (Utari, 2014), the main components in the tourist area are "4A" as follows: (1) Tourist Attractions are all forms of attraction possessed by nature in a tourist attraction, (2) Amenities are all kinds of infrastructure and facilities needed by tourists while in the Tourist Destination Region, (3) Accessibility is related to the level of ease of a tourist to reach a tourist attraction both in geographical distance or technical speed, as well as the availability of means of transportation to the destination, (4) *Ancillary Service* is an additional service or often also referred to equipment that must be provided by the local government of a tourist destination, both for tourists and for tourism actors.

There are nine principles of cultural based tourism villages that were produced from Bali's ecotourism training by the Ministry of the Environment on 3-5 September 2002, namely: 1) Having concern, commitment and responsibility for nature conservation and cultural heritage, 2) Providing interpretations that provide opportunities for tourists to enjoy nature and increase their love for nature, 3) Contribute continuously to local communities and empower local communities, 4) Be sensitive and respect the socio-cultural values and religious traditions of local communities, 5) Comply with regulations applicable legislation, 6) Development must be based on consultation with the approval of the local community, 7) Consistently providing satisfaction to consumers, 8) Marketed and promoted honestly and accurately so that in accordance with expectations, 9) Management system that is harmonious and balanced in accordance with the concept of Tri Hita Karana (A rida, 2017).

The concept of tourism in the form of ecotourism based on culture is very appropriate to be applied in Bali. The development of a cultural based tourism village is expected to be able to preserve the nature and culture of Bali. Tabanan Regency is one of nine regencies / cities in the Province of Bali. As many as 23,358 hectares or 28% of the total land area in Tabanan Regency are paddy fields, so that Tabanan Regency is known as the rice barn for Bali. Tabanan Regency has mountain, lake, valley, lowland, coastal and sea ecosystems, and has the largest rice fields and plantation potential in the Province of Bali.

Tabanan Regency also seeks to be able to increase Regional Original Revenue (PAD) from the tourism sector aside from the agricultural sector. One of the steps taken is by issuing Perda No. 11/2012 concerning Tabanan District Spatial Plan for 2012-2032. In the Regional Regulation the RTRW is designated a Tourism Allocation Area with a function as a Tourist Attraction (DTW). The DTW regulates the designation of 38 villages in Tabanan Regency as a tourism village. In its journey, in fact only a few villages were able to develop into a tourist village. One of the most famous is Jatiluwih Village which has been designated a World Cultural Heritage (WBD). Babahan Village, a village located adjacent to Jatiluwih Village, has not been able to develop as expected until now.

The development of rural tourism has a positive impact on the economic development of local communities in the village, including: increased income of rural communities; increased employment opportunities for local people in the tourism sector; the existence of local regulations,

namely restrictions on incoming foreign investment have an impact on increasing ownership and control of local communities and pride in working and doing business in their own villages; Government revenue through tourism levies (Hermawan, 2016).

The results of research conducted by Prastiyo (2019) in Cempaka Tourism Village, Tegal Regency, concluded that there were eight strategies undertaken by Cempaka village in developing their village, starting from building awareness, mapping potential, comparative studies, independent training, empowering from outside, infrastructure development, travel packaging, marketing and the role of print and electronic media. Research from Mahmudah (2016) in the village of Tlogopakis, District Petungkriyono, Pekalongan, produce a development plan appeal of ecotourism in the village Tlogopakis focusing on four aspects, namely, the development of tourist attractions attractive and supporting conservation efforts, improved support facilities such as procurement *homestay* environmentally friendly, improving accessibility such as adding road safety and providing awareness of road vigilance, as well as developing human resources both as a driving subject and object of receiving tourism benefits. Whereas Research by Nugroho (2004) resulted in a strategy of developing natural tourism in the Dieng region to overcome (internal) weaknesses by restoring the condition of natural and cultural tourism attractions, supporting tourism infrastructure, tourism services, and increasing tourism promotion cooperation to maximize opportunities (external) .

The concept of a culture-based tourism village was very well adopted in the development of Babahan Village as a tourist village. So that the development of a tourism village can run well, a culture-based tourism village development strategy is needed based on the potential of the village. Thus, the research aims to analyze the potential and develop strategies for developing Babahan village, Tabanan Regency, Bali as a culture-based tourism village.

2. Research Methods

study was conducted in Babahan Village in Penebel District, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province, Indonesia, which was divided into six hamlets, namely: Babahan Kanginan, Babahan Kawan, Babahan Tengah, Bolangan, Dadia, and Utu covering an area of 431 Ha. The implementation starts from November 2019 until January 2020. The scope of the research is limited to objects that have the potential for tourist attraction with a culture-based ecotourism model. The objects that have been determined are then mapped and analyzed for their potential. Their potentials and weaknesses are analyzed with SWOT (*Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat*). *Focus Group Discussion* (FGD) was also carried out to obtain a picture of problems in the field and the general view of *stakeholders* related to the idea of the direction of village development. This research uses qualitative research methods with field studies. Identification of the condition of Babahan Village is reviewed from the component "4A" (Tourist Attraction, Amenity, Accessibility, *Ancillary Service*).

Sampling is done using *nonprobability sampling technique* that is *accidental sampling* because tourists who visit a tourist attraction do not settle for a long time and *purposive sampling* because not all local people are used as research samples, but sorted based on the level of position in the community and which is expected to provide sufficient information to answer research questions. The interview used in this study by asking structured questions because researchers used interview

guidelines in the form of questionnaires that were arranged systematically and completely to collect the data sought (Sugiyono, 2010). In more detail, the sample number and sampling technique used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Study Sample

No.	Sample	Number	Technique
1	Tourism Office Tabanan District	1 person	purposive
2	Office PUPR Tabanan District	1 person	purposive
3	District BAPPEDA Research Tabanan	1 person	purposive
4	Penebel District Government	1 person	purposive
5	Babahan Village Government	6 person	purposive
6	Bendesa in Babahan Village	3 person	purposive
7	Pokdarwis Babahan Village	3 person	purposive
8	Kelian Village in Babahan	6 person	purposive
9	Kelian Tempek Subak	3 person	purposive
10	Tourist	5 people	accidental
	Total	30	people

In this study the data analysis technique used is the SWOT analysis. The analysis is based on the logic that maximizes the strengths (*Strengths*) and opportunities (*Opportunities*), but simultaneously can minimize your weaknesses (*Weaknesses*) and threats (*Threats*) (Rangkuti, 2014).

The SWOT matrix is described by calculating IFAS (*Internal Factors Analysis Summary*), namely internal strength and weakness factors and EFAS (*External Factors Analysis Summary*), namely external opportunities and threats. The technique is to give the weight of each of these factors a scale ranging from 1.0 (most important) to 0.0 (not important). Then calculate the *rating* for each factor by giving a scale ranging from 4 (*outstanding*) to 1 (*poor*). Positive variables (all variables included in the strength category) are given values ranging from +1 to +4 (very good) by comparing them with industry averages or with major competitors. While negative variables, the opposite. The weighting factor is obtained by multiplying the weight by *rating*. The result is a weighting score for each factor ranging from 4.0 (*outstanding*) to 1.0 (*poor*). Add up the weighting scores to get the total weighting scores.

3. Results and Discussion

Babahan Village in terms of the component "4A" (Tourist Attraction, Amity, Accessibility, and *Ancillary Service*), obtained the general conditions of the village as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: General Conditions Data for Babahan Village

No	Area Name	Variable: Tourism Potential							
		Attractions Nature	Social cultural attractions	Access	Tourism infrastructure	Tourist Visits	Community Response.	Government Support	Tourism Concern Group (Pokdarwis)
1	Babahan Kanginan		Pakiyisan	Good		Low	Enough	exist	exist
2	Babahan Kawan			Good		Low	Enough	exist	exist
3	Babahan Tengah		Village Temples, Puseh Temple, Dalem Temple Babahan	Good		Low	Enough	exist	exist
4	Dadia		Pura Jambelangu	Good	Market	Low	Good	exist	exist
5	Bolangan	Spring water	Pucak Semau Temple, Lembah Bhayam Ashram, Beji Agung	Very good	Homestay Land development stop over	height	Very good	exist	exist
6	Utu	Rice terrace, Crystal water, Selfie spot, Besikalung Waterfall, Batukapas Waterfall, Windmill Waterfall, Track Tracking WaterWarm	Besikalung Temple, Pejenengan Temple,	Fairly Good	Homestay, Tridatu	Tinggi Restaurant	Very Good	exist	exist

Source: Survey and Researcher Analysis, 2019

Based on Table 2, the potentials are mostly located in Utu and Bolangan hamlets. From the IFAS-EFAS calculations, the results of the internal factors of the village which are the strengths of the development of Babahan Village are as follows: Having apath *tracking* (with a score of 0.305), good natural potential (0.305), the existence of Besikalung Temple (0.302), beautiful rice field views (0.300), Has land development potential (0.292), Has superior agricultural products (0.221), available *Homestay is* (0.221), Strategic location (0.217), Friendly community (0.215), Availability of *selfie spots* (0.209), and Has Valley Ashram *Bhayam* (0.194).

Based on calculations that have been done through a SWOT analysis according to figure 1, so he found the final value of the internal factors are the strength (*strength*) with a value of 2,782 and weakness (*weakness*) with a value of 0.279, as well as external factors is a chance (*opportunity*) with a value of 2,207 and threat (*threat*) with a value of 0.423.

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis Diagram

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2019

Maintaining and improving the quality of tourist attraction, carried out by adopting the principle of culture-based ecotourism, namely (1) having concern, commitment and responsibility for nature conservation and cultural heritage, which includes conservation Besikalung Temple and Protection Forest; (2) making regulations related to management of chicken and pig livestock waste, as well as structuring the appearance of livestock areas so as not to look dirty and dirty, (3) making a map of village land use by taking into account the balance of the ecosystem / carrying capacity of the environment, (4) using environmentally friendly technology.

Developing and managing the existing natural potential, carried out by adopting the principle II of cultural-based ecotourism, which provides interpretations that provide opportunities for tourists to enjoy nature and increase love for nature, namely by (1) Revitalizing, adding trails, and points *rest area* on *jogging track*, (2) Adding *selfie spots* for tourists, (3) Organizing the existing natural potential, with top priority on access roads to the location of waterfalls and warm springs.

Improving the quality of service to tourists, is done by adopting the principle of culture-based ecotourism VIII, which is consistently providing satisfaction to consumers by (1) Creating a *stop over / Tourist Information area Center (TIC)*, (2) Improvement of road and bridge conditions, (3) Standardization of *homestays*. The development of tour packages, in their development must accommodate the principle III of cultural-based ecotourism, namely to contribute continuously to the local community and empower the local community. This is done by (1) Presenting professional and licensed guides, (2) Presenting tour package options for tourists who can maximize the involvement of village communities.

In its implementation, it was agreed that besides the four principles that have been accommodated above, it must also consider five other principles of ecotourism based on culture that are the basis of all policies taken, namely principle 4 (sensitive and respecting socio-cultural values and religious traditions of local communities) principle 5 (abiding by applicable laws and regulations), principle 6 (development must be based on consultation and agreement of the local community), principle 7 (marketed and promoted honestly and accurately so that it is in line with expectations and reality) and principle 9 (management system that is harmonious and balanced in accordance with the concept of Tri Hita Karana).

4. Conclusion

Babahan Village has the potential to be developed as a tourist village. The potentials that are owned are mostly in Utu and Bolangan hamlets with the main potentials of IFAS calculation results are having a path *tracking* (with a score of 0.305), good natural potential (0.305), the existence of Besikalung Temple (0.302), and a beautiful view of rice fields (0.300). The SWOT analysis is in Quadrant I (Supporting Aggressive Strategies) which results in the formulation of four strategies *Strengths-Opportunities* (SO) to develop Babahan Village as a culture-based ecotourism village, namely: (1) Maintain and improve the quality of tourist attraction, (2) Develop and managing the existing natural potential, (3) Improving the quality of services for tourists, (4) Developing Packages *tour*.

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